

Effects of herbicides on rice seed coated with activated carbon and direct seeded. Second crop, 1977, Chiayi, Taiwan.

Herbicide	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Weed control ^a		Rice toxicity ^b		Yield (t/ha) ^c	
		With carbon	Without carbon	With carbon	Without carbon	With carbon	Without carbon
Terbuchlor	0.3	1.7	1.1	5.8	8.3	5.2 ab	3.1 c
Benzglycereth (WL29226)	0.5	4.3	4.3	2.0	2.1	5.7 a	5.1 ab
Piperophos/ dimethametryn	0.5/ 0.5	1.9	1.7	3.4	5.6	5.4 ab	4.5 bc
Piperophos/ 2,4-D IPE	0.5/ 0.5	8.0	8.2	3.3	4.4	5.6 ab	5.2 ab
Perfluidone/ 2,4-D IPE	1.0/ 0.25	8.6	8.8	4.8	5.1	5.3 ab	5.5 ab
Untreated control	–	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.9 ab	4.8 ab

^a Rated at 15 days after herbicide application: 1 = no control, 10 = excellent weed control.

^b Rated at 15 days after herbicide application: 1 = no control, 10 = complete kill of rice.

^c Any two means with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

piperophos/dimethametryn, and piperophos/2,4-D IPE. Herbicides with protectant gave higher yields than those without; the degree of yield increase was more pronounced in herbicides that are more toxic to rice. Without protectant, plots treated with the highly toxic terbuchlor and piperophos/dimethametryn

gave lower yields than the untreated control; the difference for terbuchlor was significant at the 0.05% level. The untreated control with carbon-coated seeds also yielded higher than that without carbon coating, suggesting that activated carbon has beneficial effects other than as a herbicide protectant.

Nitrogen application as high as 180 kg N/ha resulted in a positive yield response and improved all characters observed (effective tillers, panicle length, test weight, and flag leaf area). The uptake of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in plants increased as nitrogen level increased; uptake of all nutrients was maximum at 180 kg N/ha. The protein in grain increased with increasing nitrogen level; it ranged from 8.97 to 11.20%.

With every increase in nitrogen level, grain yield increased significantly. At 0, 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha levels the mean yields were 4.3, 5.5, 6.2, and 6.7 t/ha, respectively. The percentage increases in yield over the control for 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha were 28, 46, and 57, respectively. The responses per kilogram of nitrogen at 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha were 21, 16, and 14 kg of paddy grain, respectively.

Nitrogen applied through urea gave the maximum grain yield (6.3 t/ha), followed by the urea + CAN combination (6.1 t/ha) and CAN (6.0 t/ha). Although the forms of nitrogen did not produce significant differences in grain yield, urea returned a higher net profit per hectare and was most economical. **W**

Soil and crop management

Effect of levels and sources of nitrogen on Jaya

R. A. Raju, senior research fellow, Department of Agronomy, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221005, U.P., India

Nitrogen fertilization, one of the most effective production inputs for rice, is expensive in Asia. To increase rice yields, not only is the optimum quantity of nitrogen important; suitable sources must also be considered. A field experiment was designed through the European Nitrogen Service program at J. N. Agricultural University, Jabalpur, M. P., India, to determine optimum and profitable doses of nitrogen supplied

through suitable sources to Jaya, a high yielding dwarf indica variety.

The soil of the experimental area was sandy clay loam, low in available nitrogen (156 kg/ha), medium in available P₂O₅ (44 kg/ha), and high in available K₂O (300 kg/ha). The soil's pH was 7.0. Four levels of nitrogen (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha) and three sources (urea, calcium ammonium nitrate [CAN], and urea as basal with CAN topdressed) were used. The nitrogen was applied in 3 split doses: 50% as basal, 25% at active tillering stage, and the remaining 25% at panicle initiation. Among the data determined were ancillary characters; nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium content in plants; and protein content of the grain.

The pinch method of dibbling rice in a paste of cow dung under wet conditions in southern Kerala, India

M. R. C. Pillai, assistant professor, Agronomy Department, Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India

A peculiar system of sowing rice - dibbling seeds in a paste of cow dung under wet conditions - has long been practiced in parts of southern Kerala.

After the final puddling, the farmer levels the field with a leveling board, leaving only a minimum amount of water. The field is left that way overnight (15–18 hours) to allow the sediments to settle. The next morning the standing water is drained. Raised beds about 2 to 2.5 m wide are then made by opening small furrows 10-cm deep with spades to allow the inlet and drainage of irrigation water during crop growth. The individual beds are then leveled with a device made

of coconut frond or by foot. The field is then ready for dibbling.

Cow dung is cleaned of undigested grass or straw and trampled by foot into a paste. Water is added if required. The paste is leveled to a circle about 10 cm thick. Sprouted paddy seeds are then sprinkled over the paste. The seeds are mixed with the cow dung paste by foot. Then the cow dung paste is heaped with a spade and again leveled to a circle. The process is repeated three or four times. To determine if the seeds have been mixed uniformly, the farmer takes a pinch of the paste and examines it in a

bowl of water. The mixture is considered uniform when it shows 3–5 seeds/pinch.

The paste is then dibbled in the prepared beds by throwing it pinch by pinch, maintaining a uniform distance (40 to 45 hills/sq m) between hills.

If adequate cow dung is not available, fine tank silt is used for part of the paste. In 3 or 4 days, vigorous green sprouts emerge from the paste, giving the fields a green, carpety appearance. After 8 to 10 days, water is let in and allowed to stand in the furrows on either side of the beds. After about 2 weeks, water in the beds is increased to about 2 cm if

there are signs of weed growth or of white ant or cricket attack.

This sowing method is usually used for short-duration varieties that were not customarily transplanted in the past. It results in vigorous seedling emergence, better nutrient absorption in early stages, and survival during periods of water scarcity. Irrigation and drainage are more efficient because the furrows on both sides of the beds allow uniform moisture control. The method also allows freedom of movement for field operations. **W**

The relationship of *khaira* incidence in rice to phosphorus levels and farmyard manure applications

S. R. Misra, R. S. Sachan, and R. A. Gupta, Department of Soil Science, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

Khaira, an ailment attributed to zinc deficiency in plants, is common in the Mollisols of the *tarai* region of northern India. Phosphorus becomes more soluble on submergence. At high levels, it has reportedly reduced drastically the uptake and translocation of zinc to the shoots of rice plants.

In a field trial, the response of rice (variety IR24) to nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium fertilizers under artificially created soil fertility levels was studied. The levels were different amounts of the three nutrients and farmyard manure that had been applied to four plots (each consisting of 0.2 ha of an 0.8-ha experimental plot) during previous crop seasons. One plot received farmyard manure and fertilizer phosphorus, the second received high levels of phosphorus only, the third was rich in inorganic residual nitrogen, and the fourth received no fertilizer or manure during the previous years. Thus the experimental plots varied widely in available soil phosphorus. Each of the four plots was subdivided into 43 plots of equal size and response of rice to soil and fertilizer nutrients was studied.

Effect of levels of soil and fertilizer phosphate and farmyard manure on the incidence of *khaira*

G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, India.

Phosphorus levels ^a (kg P/ha)	Plots affected by <i>khaira</i> (no.)			
	No plants affected	Fewer than 25% plants affected	Fewer than 50% plants affected	Almost all plants affected
0– 25	44	3	0	0
26– 50	20	15	8	1
51– 75	7	4	5	3
76– 100	2	1	8	3
101– 125	0	0	0	5
Farmyard manure applied in previous years	43	0	0	0

^a (Olsen's soil P + fertilizer P).

Interesting trends were noted in the incidence of *khaira* and levels of soil and fertilizer phosphorus (Olsen's P and single superphosphate, respectively) on the one hand, and in the previous year's application of farmyard manure on the other (see table).

The plot where farmyard manure had been applied in previous years had no incidence of *khaira* even at high levels of soil and fertilizer phosphorus. But in the plots with no farmyard manure, the relationship between *khaira* incidence and phosphorus levels was positive. At phosphate levels below 25 kg P/ha, there was almost no incidence of *khaira*. The few plots where it occurred were only mildly affected. As the phosphate level increased, the number of cases and the severity increased. At the highest phosphate level (100 to 125 kg P/ha), all

plots were severely affected.

Farmyard manure seems to have increased the availability or translocation, or both, of zinc to rice plants. Even at phosphate levels as high as 100 to 125 kg P/ha, no incidence of *khaira* was observed. Possible reasons are being investigated. **W**

Invitation to authors

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